

A P-ADIC IDENTITY FOR WIEFERICH PRIMES

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ABSTRACT. Let n be a positive integer, p be an odd prime and integers $a, b \neq 0$ with $\gcd(a, b) = 1$, $p \nmid ab$, and $p \mid (a^n \pm b^n)$, we prove the identity

$$\nu_p(a^n \pm b^n) - \nu_p(n) = \nu_p(a^{p-1} - b^{p-1}).$$

An unintended interesting immediate consequence is the following variant of Wieferich's criterion for FLT : Let $x^n + y^n = z^n$ with n prime and x, y, z pairwise relatively prime. Then every odd prime $p \mid y$ satisfies $\nu_p(z^{p-1} - x^{p-1}) \geq n - 1$ and every odd prime $p \mid x$ satisfies $\nu_p(z^{p-1} - y^{p-1}) \geq n - 1$, and every odd prime $p \mid z$ satisfies $\nu_p(x^{p-1} - y^{p-1}) \geq n - 1$, ie. every odd prime dividing xyz is a Wieferich prime of order at least $n - 1$ to some base pair. In the "first case" where $n \nmid xyz$, the lower bound for the Wieferich order can be improved to n . This gives us very strong intuition why FLT should be true even for moderately large n .

1. MOTIVATION AND RESULT

For a prime p and integer n , we shall denote the p -adic valuation by $\nu_p(n)$, the exact power of p dividing n . Since $(a^n - 1, 1, a^n)$ is an abc tuple, a very weak form of the ABC conjecture [2, 4] implies that the average power of $(a^n - 1)a^n$, given by $\frac{\log((a^n - 1).a^n)}{\log(\text{rad}((a^n - 1).a^n))}$ has to be bounded above which means for n large, $a^n - 1$ must have many factor occurring to the first power to compensate for a^n [1] so that primes dividing $a^n - 1$ to high powers must be rare.

This prompts us to look at primes which divides $(2^n - 1)$ to high powers, and we immediately observed that $p^2 \mid (2^n - 1)$ implies $p \mid n$ and more over the defect $\delta := \nu_p(2^n - 1) - \nu_p(n) = 1$ always for the first few hundreds n . This seems a little too good to be true and in fact it obviously can't hold for Wieferich prime where $p^2 \mid (2^{p-1} - 1)$. Indeed the first failure occur at $n = 364 = \text{ord}_p(2)$, the multiplicative order of 2 mod the first Wieferich prime $p = 1093$. Further experimentations with other bases reveal that failure can only occur for Wieferich primes and they can only occur when the defect $\delta > 1$. Also the defect does not depend on n for a fixed prime, Wieferich or not. This leads us to the following identity

Theorem 1.1. *Let $a \neq 0, 1$ be an integer, n a positive integer, and p an odd prime $p \nmid a$, and $p \mid (a^n \pm 1)$, then we have*

$$(1.1) \quad \nu_p(a^n \pm 1) - \nu_p(n) = \nu_p(a^{p-1} - 1).$$

The minus identity still holds for $p = 2$ except when n is even and a is 3 mod 4, the RHS should be replaced with $\nu_2(a + 1)$. The plus identity for $p = 2$ only holds for n odd as $\nu_2(a^n + 1) = \nu_2(a + 1)$.

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An immediate consequence, used in the proof that ABC implies existence of infinitely many non Wieferich primes [6], which we were not thinking about, is the well known fact that $\nu_p(a^n - 1) = 1$ implies p is non Wieferich, and we now know additionally that $\nu_p(n) = 0$. Essentially the standard known proof of this special case also give us the proof of the full case, once we know which terms to keep track from the identity.

Proof. Assume first $p|(a^n - 1)$ and let $d = \text{ord}_p(a)$ we then have $d|p - 1$ and $d|n$, so that $n = dr, p - 1 = dm$ and $p \nmid dm$ and hence $\nu_p(n) = \nu_p(r)$.

Let $\phi_p(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{p-1} x^j$ be the p th cyclotomic polynomial. We note that if k is any nonzero integer $\phi_p(1 + kp) = \sum_{j=0}^{p-1} (1 + kp)^j = \sum_{j=0}^{p-1} (1 + jkp + O(p^2)) = p + (p - 1)pkp/2 + O(p^2) = p \pmod{p^2}$, so $\nu_p(\phi_p(1 + kp)) = 1$.

We will prove the minus identity by induction on $\nu_p(n)$. Assume first $p \nmid n$ so $p \nmid r$, and $a^{p-1} - 1 = a^{dm} - 1 = (a^d - 1)t$, where $t = \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} (a^d)^j = m \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$, so $\nu_p(a^{p-1} - 1) = \nu_p(a^d - 1)$. Similarly $a^n - 1 = a^{dr} - 1 = (a^d - 1)t$ where $t = \sum_{j=0}^{r-1} (a^d)^j = r \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. So $\nu_p(a^n - 1) = \nu_p(a^d - 1) = \nu_p(a^{p-1} - 1)$.

Now let $m \geq 0$ and $n = dp^{m+1}r$ where $p \nmid r$, and let $u = dp^m r$, then since $p|a^n - 1, a^{up} - 1 = (a^u - 1) = 0 \pmod{p}$, so $\nu_p(\phi_p(a^u)) = 1$. We now have $a^n - 1 = a^{up} - 1 = (a^u - 1)\phi_p(a^u)$, so $\nu_p(a^n - 1) = \nu_p(a^u - 1) + 1 = \nu_p(a^{p-1} - 1) + \nu_p(u) + 1 = \nu_p(a^{p-1} - 1) + \nu_p(n)$. This proves the minus identity.

If $p|(a^n + 1)$, then $p|(a^{2n} - 1)$ and $p \nmid (a^n - 1)$ so that $\nu_p(a^{2n} - 1) = \nu_p(a^n + 1)$, and applying the minus identity gives $\nu_p(a^n + 1) - \nu_p(n) = \nu_p(a^{p-1} - 1)$.

For $p = 2$, a is odd, $(a^n - 1) = (a - 1)t$ where $t = \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} a^j = n \not\equiv 0 \pmod{2}$, if n is odd, so $\nu_2(a^n - 1) = \nu_2(a - 1)$. If n is even, let $n = 2^u m$, $u \geq 1$ and m odd, then $a^n - 1 = \prod_{j=0}^{u-1} (a^{2^j m} + 1)(a^m - 1)$. If $a \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, $\nu_2(a^n - 1) = u + \nu_2(a^m - 1) = \nu_2(n) + \nu_2(a - 1)$ where we use the odd case in the last term. If $a \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, all term in the product contribute a single factor of 2 except $a^m + 1$, so $\nu_2(a^n - 1) = \nu_2(a^m + 1) + \nu_2(n)$. But as before $a^m + 1 = (a + 1)t$ where $t = \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} \pm a^j = m \not\equiv 0 \pmod{2}$, so $\nu_2(a^m + 1) = \nu_2(a + 1)$.

For the plus cas for $p = 2$, we assume n is odd, then $(a^n + 1) = (a + 1)t$ where t is odd as before. So $\nu_2(a^n + 1) + \nu_2(a + 1)$. QED \square

The identity in Theorem 1.1 is apparently new and it has many immediate consequences. The surprised term $\nu_p(n)$ is seemingly the reason why there is a separation into case I and II for FLT.

Our original observation that if $p^2|(a^n - 1)$ or $p^2|(a^n + 1)$, then $p|n$ unless we have the rare case that p is Wieferich, generalizes the special case for Fermat and Mesernne numbers, for example [5]. Also we have $\nu_p(a^{\text{ord}_p(a)} \pm 1) = \nu_p(a^{p-1} - 1)$ if $p \nmid a$. Perhaps the most interesting and unintended immediate consequence is a considerable strengthening of Weiferich's criterion for FLT but we need to generalize Wieferich prime to rational or rather an 2-tuple integral base.

1.1. Extension to rational base and a strengthened Wieferich criterion for FLT. The proof of Theorem 1.1 still works if $a \neq 0, 1$ is rational as was done in [6], if we use the natural extension of the valuation $\nu_p(a/b) := \nu_p(a) - \nu_p(b)$. It is simpler to write in homogenous integral coordinates. Homogenising theorem 1.1 for rational a/b gives us

Theorem 1.2. *Let $a \neq b$ be nonzero integers and $\gcd(a, b) = 1$ and n a positive integer. If $p \nmid ab$, and $p \mid (a^n \pm b^n)$, we have*

$$(1.2) \quad \nu_p(a^n \pm b^n) - \nu_p(n) = \nu_p(a^{p-1} - b^{p-1}).$$

Again the same formula holds in the minus case for $p = 2$ except when n is even and $ab \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$ where the RHS should be replaced with $\nu_2(a + b)$. The plus identity holds only for $p = 2$ and n odd as $\nu_2(a^n + b^n) = \nu_2(a + b)$.

We still have the original observation that if $p^2 \mid (a^n \pm b^n)$ then $p \mid n$ unless p is Wieferich to the base $\{a, b\}$ (see below).

Even the case $n = 1$ seems non obvious and we record it as

Lemma 1.3. *If a prime $p \geq 2$ is such that $p \nmid ab$ but $p \mid (a \pm b)$, then*

$$\nu_p(a^{p-1} - b^{p-1}) = \nu_p(a \pm b),$$

except when $p = 2$, only the minus equality hold. In particular if $p \nmid ab$ and $p \mid (a \pm b)$, then for all $n \geq 1$, we have

$$(1.3) \quad \nu_p(a^n \pm b^n) = \nu_p(n) + \nu_p(a \pm b).$$

Proof. First equality follow from setting $n = 1$ in (1.2). The second follows from $p \mid (a \pm b)$ implies $p \mid (a^n \pm b^n)$. \square

Note (1.3) does not hold if we only know $p \mid (a^n \pm b^n)$, for example, $3 \mid (5^4 - 4^4)$ but $2 = \nu_3(5^4 - 4^4) \neq \nu_3(4) + \nu_3(5 - 4) = 0$.

We now note that the RHS of (1.2), $\nu_p(a^{p-1} - b^{p-1}) \geq 1$ always, being a homogenization of little Fermat $\nu_2(a^{p-1} - 1) \geq 1$. This suggests the homogenization of Wieferich prime to a pair of bases. We say that a prime $p \nmid ab$ is a Wieferich prime to the base (a, b) of order r if $\nu_p(a^{p-1} - b^{p-1}) = r > 1$. Clearly the usual Wieferich prime to the base a is Wieferich to the base $(1, a)$ and being Wieferich to the base (a, b) is the same as to the base (b, a) so we shall always assume $a < b$. Probabilistically, being Wieferich to a base (a, b) is as rare as being Wieferich to a base a and the probability decrease for larger prime. For example, 19, 269, 440297 are Wieferich to the base $(3, 13)$ all of order 2, and there is no more for prime upto 10^8 . It is however easy to construct artificial bases for which a small prime is Wieferich of high order. For example, the expression $(3^k + t)^2 - (3^k - t)^2 = 4t3^k$ implies 3 is Wieferich to the base $(3^k - t, 3^k + t)$ of order at least k .

Wieferich prime of order ≥ 3 are even rarer as we expect there are only finitely many such primes for each fixed base, We computed for primes upto 10^6 for the 3043 bases (a, b) with $1 \leq a < b \leq 100$ with $\gcd(a, b) = 1$, there are 61 base pairs with Wieferich primes of order ≥ 4 and all the primes occuring are small ≤ 17 , and only two base pair $(38, 41)$, $(3, 79)$ where 5 is Wieferich of order 5.

Theorem 1.4. *(Higher order Wieferich criterion for FLT) Let n be an odd prime and x, y, z be relatively prime positive integers satisfying $x^n + y^n = z^n$. Then, any odd prime $p \mid x$ is Wieferich to the base (y, z) of order at least $\geq n - 1$. Any odd prime $p \mid y$ is Wieferich to the base (x, z) of order $\geq n - 1$. Any odd prime $p \mid z$ is Wieferich to the base (x, y) of order $\geq n - 1$. For the "first case" where $n \nmid xyz$, we can increase the lower bound to n . Similarly for $p = 2$, if $2 \mid z$, $\nu_2(x + y) \geq n$. If $2 \mid x$, $\nu_2(z - y) \geq n$. If $2 \mid y$, $\nu_2(z - x) \geq n$. If a p dividing x actually divides $z - y$, then we also have $\nu_p(z - y) \geq n - 1$. Similarly for the other two cases.*

Proof. Let $p \mid y$, then $p \nmid xz$, and $p^n \mid y^n = (x^n - z^n)$. By the identity,

$$\nu_p(x^{p-1} - z^{p-1}) = \nu_p(x^n - z^n) - \nu_p(n) \geq n - \nu_p(n) \geq n - 1.$$

If $p \mid z$, $p^n \mid (x^n + y^n)$ and we apply the plus identity. If $n \nmid xyz$, all $\nu_p(n) = 0$.

Exactly one of x, y, z is even and $\nu_2(n) = 0$. If $2 \mid z$, $2^n \mid (x^n + y^n)$, the plus identity holds with $\nu_2(x + y) = \nu_2(x^n + y^n) \geq n$. If $2 \mid x$, $2^n \mid (z^n - y^n)$, and since n is odd, we must have $yz \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ so the minus identity holds, and $\nu_2(z - y) = \nu_2(z^n - y^n) \geq n$.

Among the primes dividing x , there must be some which also divide $z - y$ since $p \mid x^n = (z^n - y^n) = (z - y)(z^{n-1} + \dots + y^{n-1})$. By Lemma 1.3, we have $\nu_p(z - y) = \nu_p(z^{p-1} - y^{p-1}) \geq n - 1$. \square

The results still holds for $n = 2$ where we have solution to verify. It state that if $x^2 + y^2 = z^2$ and p is an odd prime dividing xyz then p is Wieferich to a base pair (complementary to the one it divides). This seems interesting since we know how to generate all Pythagorean tuples. We have for example $38399^2 + 2042040^2 = 2042401^2$, the z -term $p = 2042401$ turn out to be a prime so we have $2042401^2 \mid (2042040^{2042400} - 38399^{2042400})$.

The condition in Theorem 1.4 are so strong that it gives us very convincing intuition why FLT should fail for even moderately large n with increasing improbability for larger n . The natural question is how can we turn this into a proof for all sufficiently large n ?

1.2. Relevance to the $(a^n - 1, 1, a^n)$ abc tuple. A weak form of the ABC conjecture applied to the tuple $(a^n - 1) + 1 = a^n$ states essentially that the average power of $a^n - 1$, $X_a := \left\{ \frac{\log(a^n - 1)}{\log(\text{rad}(a^n - 1))} \right\}_{n \geq 1}$ is bounded. It seems we can't (?) even prove this very special case for a fixed $a = 2$ say, and one key problem seems to be that we can't give a upper bound to the power that a prime can divide $a^n - 1$. Using our identity, we can control the $\nu_p(a^n - 1) - \nu_p(n)$ if we know a bound on the RHS which is independent of n . This leads us to define for any integer $a > 1$, its largest Wieferich-order to be

$$W_a := \sup_p \nu_p(a^{p-1} - 1),$$

where the *sup* is taken over all primes, and we shall assume W_a is bounded, which seems plausible. For infinitely many a we don't even know if $W_a > 1$. It is not known if $W_2 > 2$. On the other hand, it is a century old theorem of Meyer [3] that for a fixed prime p , and an integer $r > 1$, and $1 \leq s \leq r$, there exist $1 < a < p^r$ with $\nu_p(a) = s$, so that W_a can be arbitrary large as a varies, but this does not seem to contradict $W_a < \infty$ for any fixed a . We then have a very crude uniform bound $(a^n - 1) < \text{rad}(a^n - 1)^{\nu_p(n) + W_a}$, so that we have X_a is bounded by $1 + W_a$ over squarefree n .

We can refine the usual splitting of the factors of $a^n - 1 = m_1 m_2$ where m_1 is squarefree and m_2 is the powerful part. Then we know $\gcd(m_1, n) = 1$ and m_1 is divisible by only non Wieferich primes. We also write $m_2 = m_{2,1} m_{2,2}$ where $m_{2,1}$ is the part where the prime divisor also divide n , then $m_{2,2}$ is divisible by only Wieferich primes. Also we split $m_{2,1} = m_N m_W$ into parts divisible by non Wieferich and Wieferich primes, we then have $m_N \leq n \cdot \text{rad}(n)$. So we have $m = m_1 m_N m_W m_{2,2}$ where the powerful part $m_W, m_{2,2}$ are divisible only by Wieferich primes which are rare, and m_N is bounded by a small quantity (compared to m). The largest part come from the squarefree part m_1 divisible only by non Wieferich

prime and there are known lower bound for m_1 in term of m . This gives us the intuition why $rad(m)$ is not much smaller than m , as predicted by ABC.

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